

A Review Article on Grahani Roga in Relation to Mental Health and Management

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Abstract:- Today stress has become an unavoidable part of modern life. Stress is a chain of nonspecific physical and psychological events. This Stress factor can slow down the functions of Digestive system. Ayurvedic science have emphasized the relation between gut and mind in the earlier time itself. Today's lifestyle induces stress to the gut, which will lead to Agnimandya and Samana Vata Dushti. This Samana Vata along with Pachaka Pitta and Kledaka Kapha plays the key role in the digestion process. Disordered functions of Agni is the reason for causing Grahani Roga¹. According to the modern view this can be correlated with Irritable bowel syndrome(IBS).

Keywords:- Stress, Agnimandya, Grahani Roga, IBS, Mental Health, Yoga, Lifestyle.

I. INTRODUCTION

Gastrointestinal system can be consider as a minibrain, since intestines and stomach contain many nerve tissues and fibres more than that in the spinalcord. When the mind become disturbed with any kind of stress and anxiety, brain releases lot of chemicals and hormones which will either increase or decrease the functions of gastrointestinal system. Charaka Vimana also quoted that wholesome food taken even in proper quantity do not get properly digested when the individual is affected with grief, fear, anger, sorrow, excessive sleep and excessive vigil².

Grahani is mainly a Tridoshaja disease, with Pitta predominance. Impairment of Agni is the main reason behind Grahani Roga. Impaired Agni digest the food incompletely. This partially digested food goes either in the upward or downward direction. When it goes downwards either in the partially digested or partially indigested form, that condition is known to be Grahani Roga³. This will result in improper nourishing of tissues, and accumulation of more stool in the body. That means here, Sara production is less compared to the kitta production. Nutrient fraction of Rasa Dhatu provides nourishment to Raktha dhatu. So, the successive transformation of dhatus mutually interfere in Grahani Roga due to Mandagni. When Kitta is moved to the bowels, it imbalances Apana Vata and produces more indigested faecalflow. Here Vata Dushti will lead to the symptoms like pain, bloating, constipation or diarrhea like features. Burning sensation, yellowish stool, liquid faeces, foul smelling and undigested food particles symbolizes Pitta Dushti, where as mucous, heaviness, lethargy and Mandagni symbolizes Kapha Dosh Dushti.

Irritable bowel syndrome can be consider as a functional gastrointestinal disorder since, there is no problem with any organ but the functional disturbance is there. Anxiety and depression are often a direct cause for IBS. So, avoiding mental disturbances and bring back the mind in a healthy state is very much needed for managing Grahani roga.

Table 1 Types of Grahani Roga

SL NO:	CHARAKA	SUSRUTA	VAGBHATA	MADHAVAKARA
1	Vataja	Vataja	Vataja	Vataja
2	Pittaja	Pittaja	Pittaja	Pittaja
3	Kaphaja	Kaphaja	Kapahaja	Kapahaja
4	Sannipataja	Sannipataja	Sannipataja	Sannipataja
5				Sangraha grahani
6				Ghatyantra grahani

II. COMMON ETIOLOGICAL FACTORS

- Asatmya, Guru, Shita, Atiruksha & Sandushtabhojanat
- Excessive intake of Katu, Tikta, Kasaya, Amla and Kshara
- Pramitsanat
- Visamasanat
- Ajirnat
- Atibhojanat
- Abhojanat
- Mithyayoga of Panchakarma procedures
- Debility by disease
- Vegavidharanat
- Atimaithunat
- Sleeping immediately after intake of food
- Desa Kala Ritu Viparita Karmanat

Fig 1 SAMPRAPTI

Table 2 Sampraptighataka⁴

Dosha	Tridosha
Dusya	Anna,rasa
Srotas	Annavaaha,pureeshavaha
Adhishtana	Pittadharakala'grahani
Srotodushtiprakara	Atipravrutti
Svabhava	Daruna
Agni	Mandata
Sadhyasadyata	Kruchrasadhya

Table 3 Purvarupa

LAKSHANA	CHARAKA	SUSRUTA	ASHTANGA SANGRAHA	ASHTANAGA HRIDAYA	MADHAVA NIDANA	YOGARATNAKARA
Trishna	+	+	+	+	+	+
Alasya	+	+	-	-	+	+
Balakshaya	+	+	-	-	+	+
Annavidaha	+	-	-	-	+	+
Chirapaka	+	-	+	+	+	+
Kayagaurava	+	-	-	-	+	+
Sadana	-	+	+	+	-	-
Klama	-	+	+	+	-	-
Aruchi	-	+	+	+	-	-
Karnakshveda	-	+	+	+	-	-
Antrakujana	-	+	+	+	-	-
Kasa	-	+	-	-	-	-
Chardi	-	-	+	+	-	-
Bhrama	-	-	+	+	-	-
Amlaka	-	-	+	+	-	-
Praseka	-	-	+	+	-	-
Vaktravairasya	-	-	+	+	-	-
Vidaha	-	+	-	-	-	-

Table 4 Samanya Lakshana

SYMPTOMS	CHARAKA	SUSRUTHA	VAGBHATA
Muhurbadha-muhurdravamalapravrutti	-	-	+
Atisrushtamalapravrutti	+	-	-
Vibadhamalapravrutti	+	-	-
Trishna	+	+	-
Arochaka	+	+	-
Vairasya	+	+	-
Praseka	+	+	-
Tamaka	+	+	-
Shunapadakara	+	+	+
Charadana	+	+	-
Jwara	+	+	-
Lohanugandhi udgara	+	+	-
Daha	-	+	-
Karsya	-	+	+
Loulya	-	+	-
Dhumaka	-	-	+
Murcha	-	-	+
Siroruka	-	-	+
Vishtambha	-	-	+

III. GRAHANI DOSHA UPADRAVA⁵

- Jwara
- Shotha
- Shula
- Hikka
- Vamana
- Adhmana
- Pralapa
- Teevra arochaka
- Shwasa
- Pandu

Table 5 Sadhyasadyatha⁶

SUSADHYA	KRICHRASADHYA	ASADHYA/DUSHCHIKITSYA
Balyavastha	Yuvavastha	Vridhavastha
Vatika Grahani	Sannipatika Grahani	Ghatyantra Grahani
Paittika Grahani		Sangraha Grahani
Kaphaja Grahani		If Asadhya Atisara Lakshanas are found

➤ Mental Health

Mental health is a state of mental well-being that enables people to cope with the stresses of life, realize their abilities, learn well and work well and contribute to their community. Ayurveda consider a person as healthy when his life forces (Doshas),bodily combustion (Agni),Fundamental constituents (Dhatu), excreta (mala), functions (Kriyas),are in optimum balance (Samavastha) and there is pleasance (Prasannatha) of

self (Atma),sensory or motor organs (Indriyas) and mind (manah). Ayurveda treat individuals based on their specific physical constitution stipulated by the union of tridoshas along with the mental, social and environmental conditions that affect them. According to Ayurveda maintenance of proper diet, medicines, Vyayama, following of Dinacharya, Rithucharya, Sadvrutta, etc are to be done to keep the mind healthy.

➤ Signs of Healthy Mind

- Taking the proper diet at the proper time according to the body type
- Healthy memory
- Maintaining self hygiene and cleanliness
- Fearlessness
- Staying active
- Doing things enthusiastically
- Perseverance
- Awareness about responsibilities
- Following good values

➤ Need of Pranayama

Pranayama is the ancient practice of controlling your breath. This breathing exercise can be practice in different ways, like when you are performing a Yogasana, meditation or on their own. Prana or breath is very closely connected with mind and soul. The purpose of Pranayama is nothing but to maintain the harmony between breath, mind and body. This will remove toxins out of the body, and supplies the body with proper oxygen, and it will lower the stress and anxiety, and helps to strengthen the mental capacity and coping skills. Due to Adhobhagiya, Madhyamabhagiya and Urdhvabhagiya

Pranayama mind become calm and quite and the process of digestion will be enhanced.⁷

➤ Need of Yoga

Yoga provides a sense of mental and physical wellbeing that will enable you to enjoy the life to the fullest. Steadiness and strength of mind are closely linked with the fitness of the

body. There is no any other technique which have mentioned the interdependence of mind and body other than yoga⁸.

A study of Asanas reveals the fact that these Asanas are structured in such a way that, they cause varying degree of mental and physical relaxation in different organs and parts of the body⁹.

Table 6 Need of Yoga

RECCOMENDED YOGA POSES	BENEFITS ¹⁰
Makarasana	Reduce stress, improves Digestion and excretion
Ardhamatsyendrasana	Abdominal circulation, digestion and excretion are improved
Sarvangasana	Brain circulation and digestive functions are improved
Pavanamukthasana	Digestion and excretion are improved
Bhujangasana	Digestion improved, flatulence and constipation are removed
Pashchimothasana	Digestion and excretion are improved

➤ Dietary Modifications

- Drink water early in the morning to eliminate toxins from the body and to stimulate peristalsis movement
- Eat food at proper time itself
- Try to avoid oily and spicy foods
- Increase the intake of green vegetables ,fruits, and salad
- Avoid excess intake of tea or coffee.

➤ Shodhana Chikitsa

- Vamana
- Virechana
- Niruhavasti
- Anuvasana vasti

➤ Shamana Chikitsa

- Deepana
- Pachana
- Grahi
- Tridoshasamaka
- Medhyadrugs

Table 7 Avasthika Chikitsa In Grahani Roga¹¹

AVASTHA	CHIKITSA
Kaphaja Grahani	Ruksha Deepana and Tikta Samyutha Shteevana Yoga
If Karsya and Bahukapha Avastha occur in Kaphaja Grahani	<u>Sakruth ruksha and sakruth snigdha chikitsa</u>
Amavastha	Deepanadravyasidha sneha
Bahupittavastha	Tiktha and Madhuradravyayuktha Deepanakarma
Bahuvataavastha	Snigdha Lavana and Amlarasatmaka Drvyaprayoga

Table 8 Pathyahara¹²

Annavarga	Shashtikashali, Mudga, Yusha, Puranashali, Lajamanda, Lajapeya
Shakavarga	Changeri, Kamalakanda
Phalavarga	Kapitha, Dadima, Bilvaphala
Dugdhavarga	Takra Dadhi, Gritha, Aja or Gavya dugdha
Tailavarga	Tilataila

Table 9 Pathya Vihara

Pathya Vihara	Apathya Ahara	Apathya Vihara
Divaswapna	Atisheetajala	Ratrijagarana
Upavasa	Dushtajala	Jalapana
Langhana	Rasona	Snana
	Gomutra	Atapasevana
	Guda	Dhumapana
	Patrasaka	Streesamsarga
	Yavakshara	Vegadharana
	Kandaphala	Nasya
	Badara	Anjana
	Pugaphala	
	Ikshurasa	

IV. DISCUSSION

All the Brihatrayis have the opinion that Grahani is the Adhishtana of Agni. Any derangement that occurs in Grahani will reflect in Agni and viceversa. Ajeernaadhyasana, stress and anxiety etc can be consider as a reason for causing Grahani Roga. This will lead to Prathiloma Gati of Vata, abnormal Pureeshavega Pravrutti and Dhatudushti. Evaluation of Agni, Ama, and Samanya and Visishta lakshanas are needed for the proper diagnosis of Grahani roga. Since Agnimandya is one of the important factor, Grahani Roga should be mainly treated by Deepana Pachana Chikitsa. Treatment modalities of Ajeerna and Atisara can also be applied for treating Grahaniashrita Dosh. During the Atisara

phase, Grahi and Dhatubalya Oushadhas have to be given. while, Malabandha phase have to be treated with Deepana,Anulomana and Srotoshodhana Oushadhas. Since stress factor also involves in the manifestation of Grahani Roga,along with Deepana Pachana Chikitsa Medhya Oushadhas are also to be considered.

V. CONCLUSION

Ayurveda has a preventive,curative and corrective approach to treat IBS. Ayurveda ensure a good solution for IBS, in the form of proper dietary management ,lifestyle modifications, Panchakarma like detoxification procedures, biopurification methods,medicaments etc. This holistic approach of Ayurveda can better manage the disease IBS, by providing a complete physical, psychological ,and spiritual well-being for a person.

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